

SOĞUTUCU AKIŞ HIZININ HİBRİT (HAVA VE SIVI) SOĞUTMA ÜZERİNDE ETKİSİ: MODÜL-SEVİYESİ BATARYA TERMAL YÖNETİMİ

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Özet: Bu çalışmada, elektrikli araç (EV) uygulaması için hibrit (kapalı devre hava ve sıvı soğutmalı) bir batarya termal yönetim sistemi incelenmiştir. Batarya termal yönetim sisteminin performansını ortaya koymak amacıyla, deneysel çalışmalar için temsilci bir batarya modülü tasarlanmış ve üretilmiştir. Miniatur modül gövdesi 3B yazıcı ile üretilmiş olup, modül içerisinde hava bir fan yardımıyla, su ise alüminyum paralel kanallı bir ısı değiştirici aracılığıyla dolaşmaktadır. Temsilci modül, iki adet 73 Ah kapasiteli NMC pouch tipi hücreyi barındırmakta olup, bu hücrelerin arasına pasif termal yönetim amacıyla bir faz değişim malzemesi (PCM) yerleştirilmiştir. Deneysel bir adet dummy (sahte) hücre ve bir adet canlı 73 Ah'lık pouch hücre kullanılmıştır. 1C deşarj oranında canlı hücrenin sıcaklığı altı farklı noktadan ölçülmüş, ayrıca şartlandırılmış ve şartlandırılmamış hava sıcaklıkları da takip edilmiştir. Hava ve su akış hızları birbirinden bağımsız olarak değiştirilmiş ve her bir parametrenin batarya sıcaklığı üzerindeki etkisi ayrı ayrı değerlendirilmiştir. Sonuçlar, fan hızının hücre maksimum sıcaklığı üzerinde su akış hızına kıyasla daha baskın bir etkiye sahip olduğunu göstermektedir. Fan hızı %100'den %10'a düşürüldüğünde hücre sıcaklığında 4.4°C'lik bir artış gözlemlenirken, su akış hızı %10'a düşürüldüğünde ise 1.9°C'lik bir sıcaklık artışı gözlemlenmiştir. Bu sonuçlar, hibrit termal yönetim sistemlerinde her bir bileşenin termal performansa etkisini ortaya koymak açısından değerlidir ve hibrit sistemler için kontrol algoritmalarının geliştirilmesine katkı sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Batarya Termal Yönetim Sistemi (BTYS), Hibrit Soğutma, Akış Hızı Etkisi

EFFECT OF COOLANT FLOW RATES FOR HYBRID (AIR AND LIQUID) COOLING: MODULE-LEVEL BATTERY THERMAL MANAGEMENT

Abstract: In this study, we investigate a hybrid (closed circuit air and liquid cooling) battery thermal management system for an EV application. To uncover the performance of the battery thermal management system a representative battery module was designed and manufactured for experimentation. The miniature module shell was manufactured by 3D printing in which air circulates via the inserted fan and water circulates in an aluminum parallel channel heat exchanger. The representative module stores two 73Ah NMC pouch cells, with a phase change material (PCM) pouch placed between them for passive thermal management. In the experiments, one dummy cell and one live cell (73 Ah pouch cell) were used. The temperature of the cell is documented from six distinct locations, and both the conditioned and unconditioned air temperatures were monitored for 1C discharge rate of a 73 Ah NMC pouch cell. Air and water flow rates were varied independently to uncover their effects on the battery temperature solely. The results show that fan speed is more dominant on the maximum cell temperature than the water flow rate. When the fan speed decreased to 10%, a 4.4°C increase was observed compared to 100% operation where a 1.9°C increase is observed when the water flow rate reduced to 10%. The results are valuable for uncovering the effect of thermal performance of each contributor in hybrid thermal management and useful for developing control algorithm for hybrid systems.

Keywords: Battery Thermal Management System (BTMS), Hybrid Cooling, Flow Rate Effect

Introduction

In recent years the increasing air pollution and global air temperature average caused by greenhouse gases lead to a growing concern about climate change (Lindsey and Dahlman, 2024; (Y. Wang et al., 2023). CO₂ and NO_x emissions from a fossil fuel using internal combustion vehicle contribute to the greenhouse effect (Jouhara &

Olabi, 2018). To prevent further pollution caused by transportation, new energy vehicles (especially electric vehicles, EVs) gained substantial interest (CHANG et al., 2025; Zeng et al., 2023). EVs most commonly utilize Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries for their long life, high energy and power density, lack of memory effect and stability (Ding et al., 2019; Tomaszewska et al., 2019a). Temperature and its uniformity are crucial for life and

performance of a Li-ion battery (Lyu et al., 2023; Mei et al., 2023). When current flows through a Li-ion battery, ohmic heating and electrochemical reaction occurs. These result in considerable heat generation that has to be controlled to prevent safety hazards, such as thermal runaway (Li et al., 2023; Ouyang et al., 2022). The ideal range of operation of a Li-ion battery is given as 20 – 40°C, where the maximum allowable temperature difference across the battery pack is given as 5°C for the safety and longevity (Tomaszewska et al., 2019b). The high heat generation rate of Li-ion batteries under load, and strong dependence of their health and safety creates the need for battery thermal management systems (BTMSs) for every application Li-ion batteries are in use.

BTMSs are responsible for keeping the Li-ion batteries at their ideal operation temperature and keeping the temperature of the batteries inside the system as uniform as possible (Hao et al., 2018). BTMSs are also responsible for preparing the batteries, preheating in extreme cold environments, hazardous gas exhaust that may be emitted from the batteries and preventing the cells from sudden ambient temperature changes by insulation (Pesaran, 2001). BTMSs are categorized by their coolants or their dependency on external power supply. By their power requirement BTMSs can be grouped as active and passive BTMS, where active systems require an external power supply. Active systems usually rely on forced convection where the coolant of the BTMS is pumped to increase the heat transfer coefficient and remove excess heat from the batteries. Passive systems utilize phase change and natural convection by special systems, such as phase change materials, heat pipes, etc. In general, active BTMSs allow strict control over the battery pack, however passive BTMSs offer simpler structure and independence from an external power source (Alaoui, 2018; Isfahani et al., 2023).

BTMSs are categorized by their coolants as, air cooling, liquid cooling and phase change cooling (Choi et al., 2023). Air cooling is advantageous for its lightweight, cost, being non-conductive and simplicity properties, however its low thermal conductivity limits its performance (Chen et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2015). High thermal conductivity coefficients are benefitted in liquid cooling. It is divided into two categories, immersion cooling and indirect cooling. In immersion cooling, the coolant directly touches the batteries and carries the excess heat by simply flowing across the batteries. Even though immersion cooling method is very effective in removing excess heat its disadvantages like, low energy density, high cost of dielectric coolants high pumping cost and safety concerns limits its use in BTMSs (Chen et al., 2016a; N. Yang et al., 2015a). Indirect cooling method utilizes special channels located in cooling plates where the liquid coolant flows. Specially designed channels increase the temperature uniformity and separating coolants and batteries allows the use of low-cost conductive coolants. However, concerns about safety, leakage and high pumping cost persists (Lu et al., 2022; Xiao et al., 2025). With phase change materials (PCM)

BTMS the latent heat capacity of melting/solidifying process is utilized. PCMs are materials that can melt/solidify in the desired temperature and have substantial latent heat capacity for store and expel heat. Since phase change is an isothermal process, PCM BTMSs are very effective in satisfying temperature uniformity across the battery pack. However, their finite heat storage capacities and low thermal conductivity are limiting factors for their use. Frequently PCMs are added with high thermal conductivity materials to increase their heat dissipation rates (Hekmat & Molaeimanesh, 2020; Patel & Rathod, 2023; Weng et al., 2020).

Even though low thermal conductivity of air limits its performance as a coolant for BTMSs, because of its simplicity, cost and safety it is still widely used and a relevant research subject (Wankhede et al., 2025). Yang et al. (N. Yang et al., 2015b) studied the effect of battery spacing on the temperature increment and heat dispersion efficiency for constant air flow rate. Xu and He (Xu & He, 2013) uncovered the link between air flow duct shape and battery module temperature. Their results indicated that reducing channel shape decreases the temperatures of the module. Zhang et al. investigated the effect of added spoilers to the side of the air intake. They created a correlation for the number and positioning of the spoilers and achieved an optimal reduction of 1.8 K.

Owing to high thermal coefficients related to liquid cooling, it is used widely in the BTMSs (Ouyang et al., 2025). Malik et al. (Malik et al., 2018) investigated the optimal temperature for the liquid coolant, their results showed 30°C initial temperature performs the best. Chen et al. (Chen et al., 2016b) compared the direct and indirect cooling methods; they uncovered direct cooling had the better temperature uniformity but with the added risk of leakage. Wang et al. (C. Wang et al., 2017) studied the cooling plates with varying channel numbers, results revealed lower temperatures can be achieved with increasing channel numbers and uncovered an optimum mass flow rate for maintaining ideal temperature range.

Interest in passive cooling methods like PCM has grown in recent years due to its advantages like, not requiring an external power supply, offering good temperature uniformity and minimal noise and pollution (Chen et al., 2016b; Malik et al., 2018). Heyhat et al. (Heyhat et al., 2020) performed a comparison between nanoporous PCM, finned PCM and porous metal PCM. The metal porous PCM performed the best among the alternatives. Wang et al. (H. Wang et al., 2024) demonstrated that PCM can still satisfy the BTMS need with ambient temperature beyond 40°C. Javani et al. (Javani et al., 2014) studied the temperature variation of a cell with PCM shell thickness varying between 3 – 12 mm. Results indicate that with increasing shell thickness temperature variation decreases and even with 3 mm shell a 10% more uniform temperature can be achieved.

Hybrid BTMS systems aim to combine the uniform temperature distribution benefits of PCM cooling and

combine it with active BTMS systems to overcome its low heat dissipation rate and finite heat storage capacity disadvantages. Because of their potential they are widely studied in the recent years (Ouyang et al., 2025). Qin et al. (Qin et al., 2019) studied a hybrid BTMS that combines air cooling and PCM. The results of their charge – discharge tests revealed that hybrid system performance surpasses both only air cooling active BTMS and PCM cooling BTMS. Yang et al. (W. Yang et al., 2021) combined cellular liquid cooling and PCM cooling. After the optimization process they achieved battery temperature as low as 39°C and 3.5°C temperature variation. Hu et al. (Hu et al., 2022) experimented with delaying the liquid cooling in a liquid cooling and PCM hybrid BTMS. In their work the liquid cooling employed once the PCM reaches its phase change temperature. The results indicated that with this method both temperature uniformity and substantial energy efficiency can be achieved.

The literature survey indicates the raising importance of BTMSs with incrementing use of EVs. Appealing benefits of hybrid BTMSs compared to pure active and passive BTMSs attracting focus of both researchers and industry. In this study we designed a hybrid BTMS module that incorporates air cooling with liquid and PCM pouch for passive thermal management. Our experimental work aims to uncover the effects of air and liquid coolant flow rates on battery temperatures.

Method

In this experimental study a representative part of an hybrid BTMS is used to investigate the temperatures of battery under controlled conditions. The hybrid BTMS is composed of a fan to circulate air in the closed BTMS, parallel aluminum cooling channels that water is circulated to condition the air in the BTMS, a fan to circulate the air, two NMC 73 Ah pouch cells (one is dummy) and a PCM pouch. Air is directed to the bottom of the module with the fan where the parallel channel cooling meander is located. After the air is conditioned with the heat exchanger it moves upward towards the batteries to remove excess heat. Finally, after conditioning the batteries the air moves to the fan to complete the circulation. The schematic of the fluid flow in the system along with temperature measurement points on the cell is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the module fluid flow.

The representative module is designed for two 73 Ah NMC pouch cells, however due to not being able to perform welding operation on the live cells one dummy cell as space holder and one live cell is used. In between the two cells a PCM pouch is placed for passive thermal management. The module holds together with covers that have square openings for allowing air flow. The top view photograph of the module is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Top view of module.

The cooling meander is composed of three 8 mm diameter aluminum pipes connected to two 10 mm diameter plastic pipes for water inlet and outlet. The cooling meander is located at the bottom of the BTMS and placed as in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Cooling meander.

In the experiments the 73 Ah NMC pouch cell is discharged with 1C (73 Ah) rate constant current using BK Precision 8614 programmable electronic load. Temperature measurements are made from white points in Figure 4 using HIOKI-LR8431-20 data logger. The plastic parts of the module and pack components were 3-D printed and glued / taped together to build the BTMS. Water is circulated in the cooling meander at 25°C using a water circulator. Air circulation is achieved by Akasa AK-FN120-BKT03 fan. Water and fan speed altered independently in the study to uncover the relation between their changes and battery temperature.

Figure 4. Temperature measurement points.

Results and Discussion

The study aims to uncover the relation between the battery temperatures and two distinct coolant flow rates. For this purpose, initially control tests were performed. To compare the cases with each other the highest measured temperature on the cell (not the tabs) were recorded. Highest temperatures for the control cases are 42.9°C and 50°C for 100% and 0% fan and water flow conditions, respectively. Then the fan and water flow rate adjusted such that one of them is limited to 10% while the other is at full capacity. The highest temperatures related to the cases are presented in

Figure 5.

Figure 5. Highest temperatures of the NMC pouch cell with varying flow rates.

The highest temperatures measured are elevated with the limited flow rates as expected. The increment in the highest measured temperatures compared to 100% fan and water case are 4.4°C and 1.9°C for cases where fan speed is limited to 10% and water flow rate is limited to 10%, respectively. When the 100% control case and 0% control case maximum temperature difference of 7.1°C considered, the relative importance of these two investigated case results are apparent. The distinct difference between the two limited cases put forth the importance of air flow over the water flow rate. This originates from the direct heat transfer between the battery and air flow. When air speed lowered the heat transfer coefficient on the battery surface and on the cooling

meander decreased proportionally this means the conditioned air temperature increased along with decreased convective heat transfer rate on the battery surface. However, when the water flow rate was limited, only the cooling meander surface temperature and the conditioned air temperature increased. Where convective heat transfer rate on the battery surface stayed as in the maximum possible case which causes slight increment in battery temperature. This result is valuable as it shows that any adjustment made on the fan speed effects multiple parts of the system, where adjustments on the water flow rate are limited with the vicinity of the cooling meander.

Conclusion

This experimental study investigates the importance of relation between the two coolants in a hybrid BTMS. The coolant flow rates adjusted independently for this purpose and the highest temperatures of the battery is recorded for each case. Results showed an increment of highest measured temperatures by 4.4°C and 1.9°C compared to 100% base case for 10% fan speed and 10% water flow rate situations. The distinct difference between the two cases unveiled the importance of fan speed in dual coolant BTMS. The result is explained by the direct relation between the fan speed and convective heat transfer rate all around the BTMS.

The result of this experiment is valuable when control mechanisms and algorithms for a dual coolant BTMS is considered. This study put forth the relative attention that should be given to the coolant flow measurements and controls. It is obvious when a similar BTMS is designed the air side measurement devices and control algorithms should be more precise than their counterparts.

Symbols

Ah	Ampere hour
C	Current ratio of total capacity and drawn current
°C	Celsius degree

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